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www.bioexcel.eu

Project Number 675728

D4.1 – Dissemination and Outreach Plan

WP4: Dissemination and Training

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the main objectives and direction of work for the center's dissemination and outreach activities. It presents:

- establishment of the brand;
- design and structure of the website;
- selection of social media channels;
- main dissemination material such as poster and brochure
- targeted events such as conferences and workshops
- publication media for outreach
- communication with industry

The document also includes a set of KPIs that will be monitored and presented in future reports.

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1 Introduction

Dissemination and outreach are very important for uptake of results from a given project and creating awareness in the community. Establishing a distinctive branding is needed for the identity of the organization and popularization of ongoing activities are the means for bringing added value to the wider community and stakeholders.

Thus, the overall dissemination strategy and outreach plan are set early in the project's lifetime as reported in the current document.

2 Branding

A distinct and consistent branding is important to establish the center's identity in the community and media. The main branding elements are

2.1 BioExcel logo

The center logo (Figure 1) was designed before the start of the project. It emphasizes the excellence in Life Science as our main foundation by representing a large letter X, which simultaneously suggests a human figure and a double stranded DNA helix.

Figure 1. BioExcel Logo

The logo is provided in various formats (png, eps, ai, pdf, svg) as needed for usage in different media.

2.2 Video intro clip

The link between DNA and a human figure is made very apparent in the video intro clip: <https://youtu.be/WxyZ0JwiHbQ>. It features an animated transition of a DNA double strand into a letter X that eventually becomes a simplified human figure. The video clip will be used as an intro to all BioExcel video materials.

2.3 Presentation material templates

Templates for various presentation materials were created based on the selected color scheme and logo:

- PowerPoint presentations

- Posters
- Promotional brochure
- Newsletters

3 Webportal

The main platform for outreach and promotion of the center is the webportal (Figure 2) that can be accessed at www.bioexcel.eu. It hosts all information related to the operation of the center and currently it includes:

- Center overview
- Ongoing projects and their results
- Success stories of our work
- Publications done as part of the project
- Services offered by the center
- Events and training
- Featured articles and interviews with notable researchers in our domain
- Twitter feed
- Contact information etc.

Most of the newly created information is added as blog posts which are added to corresponding categories (e.g. “events” or “publications” etc.). Plugin hooks are used to automatically push a twitter update from each post.

In the course of the project the content and structure of the portal will be extended.

Since the webportal’s launch, we have had 301 unique users across 488 different sessions, with 813 total pageviews. Over 60% of our visitors have been first-time visitors, and the average visit length is over 3 minutes. The website currently has a ‘bounce rate’ (the number of users who only view a single page before leaving) of 73.36%, which is high, and we will take steps to reduce this over the course of the project.

4 Mailing list and newsletters

The webportal also hosts a mailinglist system, which is also used for direct promotional outreach. Selected website posts will be sent to the mailing list in the form of a monthly email newsletter.

In addition, twice a year we will prepare a printed version of a newsletter for dissemination purposes (milestones #7-12)

bioexcel *Centre of Excellence for Computational Biomolecular Research*

About · Research · Software · Services · Events · Contact

Excellence in Science

BioExcel Centre of Excellence is supporting academia and industry in the use of high-performance computing (HPC) and high-throughput computing (HTC) in biomolecular research

Course: Integrative modelling of biomolecular interactions
4 – 9 July 2016 | Barcelona, Spain

Journal paper: Parmbsci: a refined force field for DNA simulations

Journal paper: BIGNASim: a NoSQL database structure and analysis portal ...

VIB Conference: Applied Bioinformatics in Life Sciences

Journal paper: Molecular dynamics characterization of the conformational landscape of ...

11th Concertation Meeting for H2020 e-Infra Projects

Figure 2. BioExcel Webportal

5 Social media channels

Social media presence is very important for every organization. We are using the following channels that correspond to the activities and goals of the project:

- **LinkedIn** company page
<https://www.linkedin.com/company/bioexcel-center-of-excellence-for-computational-biomolecular-research>
- **Twitter** account
<https://twitter.com/BioExcelCoE>
- **Google+** account
<https://plus.google.com/108493212243985215897>
- **Youtube** channel
https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCd2hq8Q_ZyTU4YafEhweE5g
- **GitHub** organization
<https://github.com/bioexcel>

Communication through these channels has already begun and we have had some success in disseminating our message through social media channels:

- The BioExcel Twitter account has been quite successful so far. At the time of writing the account has 32 followers and generates an average of 16 impressions per day. We have also been retweeted and ‘mentioned’ several times.
- The BioExcel LinkedIn account currently has 12 followers and we hope to grow this as the project continues.
- The BioExcel Google+ account currently has five followers. As Google+ is not as mainstream a social network as Twitter or LinkedIn, we are unsure of what to expect from this channel. However, we hope to maximise our impact across all our social media channels including Google+.

Additional channels for publication of outreach material (newsletters, press releases etc.) includes the following media:

- Scientific Computing World
- HPC Wire
- The Platform
- ComputerWorld
- ISGTW
- InsideHPC
- PrimeurMagazine
- EnterpriseTech
- The Memo
- Tecnonews
- Nature
- PLoS/PLoS Computational Biology

The webportals of the core partner institutions as well as those of the external collaborators will be also used as publication platforms.

6 Interviews and featured scientists

Regular interviews with key researchers in the area of HPC for BioMolecular simulations will be featured on the website in order to promote the solid scientific expertise in the center. The first interview in the series was with the Nobel laureate for chemistry 2013 Michael Levitt.

In addition to the interviews, we will feature selected publications from top-level journals, in which the researchers (not affiliated with the center) have used our applications or tools. The featured articles will include highlights of their research results, how the tools have been used in their work and also recommendations for improvement of the applications. Our goal is thus to extend the “friends-and-family” network of the CoE with strong external research groups.

7 Printed material

7.1 Poster

A poster presenting the expertise and services of BioExcel will be prepared to be used for exhibition in various events (conferences, workshops etc.) for dissemination purposes. The poster will be updated at later stage of the project by highlighting success stories.

7.2 Brochure

Similarly to the poster, a promotional brochure will be prepared that will, in its first version, introduce the project, and later highlight new developments.

8 Publications

Results of the research work done in the project will be submitted for publication in peer reviewed scientific journals, and will be one of the main channels for reaching out to researchers and achieving impact in our domain. The following journals and conferences have been often used by partners and will be considered for future publications:

- European Conference on Computational Biology
- Intelligent Systems for Molecular Biology
- ACM Transactions on Architecture and Code Optimisation
- ACM Transactions on Computing Systems
- ACM Transactions on Parallel Computing
- IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems
- IEEE Transactions on Computers
- Journal of Parallel and Distributed Computing
- Journal of Chemical Theoretical and Computation
- Journal of Computational Chemistry
- Bioinformatics
- PLoS Computational Biology and PLoS ONE
- Biochemistry
- SoftwareX (new Elsevier Journal targeted to open-source software)
- Concurrency in Computation Practice and Experience
- Euro-PAR, PLDI, HPDC, IPDPS, eScience, Supercomputing, POPL, CF, ROSS, CCGrid, ICCS, PPOPP, CGO, PACT, OOPSLA, ICS, ICPP and HiPEAC, ISC
- Participation in EC IST Conferences, and if agreed with the EC, demonstration at these events of the project results in the Exhibition area.
- Large international (computational) structural biology conferences like, for example, the Biophysical Society meeting, various relevant Keystone meetings, INSTRUCT meetings etc.

Publication types will include:

- Journal articles
- White papers
- Conference proceedings
- Book chapters

9 Events

9.1 Special Interest Group SIG BioExcel

An important goal of BioExcel is to establish itself as a focal point for the wide computational life science community. We will work towards that by forming a Special Interest Group (SIG) for biomolecular simulations: SIG BioExcel. The group will be nucleated around annual meetings, which will take place alongside one of the major European conferences for computational biology, ECCB.

The goal of the event will be to bring together and connect leading academic and industrial developers of software for biomolecular simulations with users as well as e-Infrastructure resource providers, i.e. all major center stakeholders. The venue will give opportunity to participants to

- showcase their success stories (academic and commercial)
- discuss upcoming challenges
- present and discuss best practices for exploitation of modern e-infrastructures
- create networking and collaboration opportunities with each other

The last point is very important since it will establish the SIG, and the CoE, as an important node in the computational life science community.

9.2 Competency Workshop

One of the initial events for engagement with users and understanding their needs will be a competency workshop. During the two day event users will be able to shortly present their ongoing work; explain their “pain points” with the software; and get a direct help from the core developers as part of “surgery” afternoon sessions. The workshop will help our center to understand users’ training needs and to provide input for the competency framework and mapping. The workshop is planned for PM7.

9.3 Conferences and workshops

Participation in conferences and workshops is also a main vehicle for promotion of the CoE, advertisement of its services and extending the outreach. Some of the main events that we will participate in are listed in section “Publications”.

9.4 Webinars

Online webinars are efficient means for the delivery of specific training to a large and distributed audience, as well as engaging with users. The center is planning to begin monthly webinars each of them covering a specific aspect of the three main codes in WP1 or selected tools/workflows from WP2.

10 Interfacing with industry

Industry is an important beneficiary of the center’s operations and an important target group for the sustainability of the CoE. Through outreach activities we will engage with companies from:

- Pharmaceutical industry
- Chemical industry
- Food industry

Pistoia Alliance (a pre-competitive pharmaceutical industry alliance) is a CoE partner who will be a major link for the center with businesses. The academic partners in the consortium also have a broad network of commercial collaborators who will be included in our dissemination activities.

11 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

As described in the previous sections, a diverse set of communication measures will be put in place to promote the project and its results to the various target communities. Table 1 below lists the various communication measures and target groups.

Communication Measure	Target Groups
Website, promotional material (flyer, factsheet, posters)	Wide scientific community, People interested in the overall goals and progress of the project
Newsletters and social media	Wide scientific community, People interested in the overall goals and progress of the project
Scientific publication	Scientific community, industrial research
Whitepapers	Independent Software Vendors (ISVs), Industrial Users, Academic software developers
Documentation and demonstrations	ISVs, Industrial Users, Academic software developers
Invited presentations	Wide scientific community, People interested in the overall goals and progress of the project
Webinars	ISVs, Industrial Users, Academic software developers
Workshops and Tutorials	Wide scientific community, industrial research

Table 1. Communication measures and target groups.

Table 2 below lists the set of KPIs, which will be monitored in the dissemination activities and reported in subsequent reports:

KPI	Quantitative objective
Conference proceedings & Peer review papers citing BioExcel	10
Conference presentations by project partners (including collaboration events)	10

Whitepapers	1
Press releases	2
Website visits	3000 p.a.
Presence in social media	Groups established in LinkedIn and Twitter as a minimum with bi-weekly updates or posts.
Significant presence at events (e.g. hosted, sponsorship or booths)	2

Table 2. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).